

ACHOLA

ACA-401D

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DEOH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

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Deleted: ACA-401D Period 1

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 10%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

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List your 5-7 critical concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay composition (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Plagiarism avoidance (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
3. Writing style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-56)
4. UK and US English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
5. Latin abbreviations and expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58-62)

COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been impressed by the approach EUCLID has taken to offer this Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) course, which looks deep yet is provided through a platform that appeals to the learners. The outline is available, and the learners' expectations are articulated in a well-detailed course pack, though the form is simple and easy to interact with. The presentation on the coursework transcends what I had imagined and envisioned going through. My excitement about taking PhD coursework has accelerated, and I cannot wait to delve deeper into the program anymore. However, I must take one step at a time to make the most sense and learn from this program by building up concepts one after the other until the very end of the program to get this degree in Environmental Health!

First, I have interacted with the ACA-401D course park as presented by EUCLID in a version revised by Pr. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma. I also reviewed the videos on using Zotero and Grammarly through links that provided handy tutorials on citation methods and correct English writing. The course park has delved deeper into the expectations by ECULID for the students to learn the most from the materials provided

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currently and the entire coursework period. I have observed that many approaches to learning and standards vary from one institution to another. However, the final goal is achieved universally by all the different institutions. However, the EUCLID approach is more profound and practical than other institutions. I also noted the interesting differences and similarities in writing style guides, the US and UK English, and the need to choose one over the other and be consistent through and through. However, in the English language, EUCLID prefers the US over British English.

This response paper will focus on five significant concepts delivered through the ACA-401D course park for period one and the videos presented therein. The considerable concepts include the composition of essays, avoiding plagiarism, and writing styles. Additionally, I have captured lessons learned from the UK and US English and the use of Latina abbreviations and expressions, which I have found new and exciting.

2) COMPOSITION OF AN ESSAY

The course park, ACA-401D, commences with academic essay writing. This is scholarly writing that is nonfictional, produced as part of academic work, and has characteristics such as having a prose register, citations, references to other works, and using stable rhetorical moves to define the scope of the writing, among others. (Cleenerwerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.). The goal is to answer a predicted phenomenon and communicate an idea from the evidence provided (Cleenerwerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.).

In writing, I noted that the essay has flexible steps that stem from defining and analyzing the questions and the assignment to be written about to understand the assignment adequately. Secondly, it is necessary to have a written plan that contains thoughts and ideas about the topic. This is followed by delving into reading and researching what to write as one questions what they already know about it, what they need to read to write about the essay, and if the materials provide valuable insights about the topic or argument. Additionally, ask yourself if the materials can support the answer. It is vital to highlight essential information for further reading and critical analysis. I have found this to be practical.

Lastly, I observed that the writing of the essay would start with making a first draft according to the structure and format, which includes the introduction, the body of the essay, and finally, the conclusion sections. Each paragraph in the essay should deal with one central aspect of the answer. It is also paramount to include examples as evidence in the essay. (Cleenerwerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.).

Commented [DG1]: From this point, ensure that all the in-text citations have the following format - (Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2024, 10). Ensure you use the correct page numbers!

Commented [DG2]: Note that periods/full stops are only placed AFTER citations, even if direct quotes are involved.

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is failing to acknowledge the sources of information used in writing or verbally, and a writer should give credit when presenting words or ideas from someone. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.). It is one of the academic mistakes that could contribute to severe penalties. I observed that there are instances when citations are required, while on the other hand, when they are not warranted. Instances that require citation include when using a quote, paraphrasing, and using statistics/data or visual aids to support an argument or idea obtained from other sources. There are two approaches to citations: quotations and paraphrasing. While quotation involves using the actual text with the author’s name in parentheses and page numbers, paraphrases are the idea and information an author produces on a topic but written in their own words; the author’s name is put in parenthesis followed by page numbers. There are a few critical areas to be noted while using quotations, including limiting the use of quotations and using the quotes only when there is vital language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well. Despite this, it is unnecessary to quote when the information is common knowledge, which can be noted when it is repeated many times by different sources. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.). It is also essential to maintain a logical flow of ideas. Using transitional words or phrases such as ‘Never the less,’ ‘However,’ ‘Moreover,’ etc. allows for thought flow and should be encouraged. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.).

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4) WRITING STYLES

A style is the standard approach to include some aspects of writing that need consistency in technical/scientific writing according to the guidelines provided by the publication company associated with this writing. It ensures coherence and consistency. There are basic rules and writing features to ensure the output’s consistency. Technical writers have a style guide for a particular customer or project to ensure that the data presented will be acceptable and up to the institution’s standards. The style goes beyond punctuation and correct grammar and vocabulary. This includes preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font size, and voice preferences. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.).

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5) USE OF UK VS. US ENGLISH

I noted that the period after the Second World War saw American English gain more recognition than British English. However, the two have similarities and differences, especially in the scientific world. The differences are attributable partly to national history,

cultural developments, and the economy. These variations are numerous and range from differences in pronunciations with exact spellings, different spellings with identical pronunciations, same terms with different but similar spellings and pronunciations, to the use of precise words with different or additional meanings, among others. The two countries also have different dating styles. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.).

In my situation, I will use US English since, in Kenya, it is the format we have used consistently in our education system. However, we use a mixture of both in everyday communication and instruction, albeit unknowingly.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATION AND AEXPRESSIONS

Latin abbreviations are used in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing. However, it is encouraged that in business, formal, and technical writing, the English equivalent of the abbreviation is used to avoid misinterpretation by readers. Nonetheless, I noted that it is best to create content using plain language principles, a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing. Moreover, use short sentences with simple words and avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations. (Cleenewerck, Gulma, and Coursepack, n.d.)

7) CONCLUSION

Since this was my first encounter with the EUCLID approach to academic learning, I have noted the high demand expected from the entire Ph.D. program through this introductory lesson as a built-in course pack period one. It has been far enriching and eye-opening. I am looking forward to more detailed interaction with the yet-to-come content. I am now different from before, and this course is about academic writing.

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REFERENCES

Commented [DG5]: Refer to page two of the coursepack for guidance on how to reference the coursepack!

ACHOLA

ACA-401D

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, Kabiru Gulma, and D Coursepack. n.d. "B. Notes-Bibliography Style."

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.